

OCEANOGRAPHIC DATA PROFILE ANALYSIS USING INTERACTIVE COMPUTER GRAPHICS TECHNIQUES

Lawrence J. Rosenblum

Naval Research Laboratory
Washington, D.C. 20375

ABSTRACT

The analysis of oceanographic data often involves visual comparison of a collected data profile with other collected, historical, or simulated profiles. Using conventional graphics techniques, geometrical data comparisons involving such operations as sliding data curves (i.e., viewing different sections of the entire data profile), rescaling data, expanding curve sections, and overlaying curves require extensive, tedious replotting. Using airborne marine magnetic anomaly data as an example, this paper will show how software, designed using newly available interactive computer graphics tools, allows the scientific data analyst to perform, rapidly and easily, this type of geometrical data profile analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Oceanographic data is typically collected as a function of track, time, or depth. The data is then generally treated as a profile, rather than individual points, for data analysis. Many analysis procedures search for geometrical similarities or differences between a collected data profile and other collected, historical or simulated profiles. Using conventional plotting methods, such an analysis is both laborious and time consuming, requiring extensive replotting of the data with changes in scale and data profile segments. However, graphics "language" packages (i.e., collections of user callable subroutines to perform graphics functions), based on proposed graphics standards, are now offered by most computer manufacturers and others. These languages contain powerful tools which the applications programmer can utilize to create interactive graphics programs. Such programs greatly reduce the time and effort required to perform analyses which require a sequence of repetitive operations by the user.

Examples of oceanographic data processing which are well suited to interactive graphics techniques can be found in the processing of ship and airborne bathymetric, gravimetric [1,2] and magnetic anomaly measurements. The data used in this paper is taken from an airborne magnetic survey of the mid-Atlantic ridge near

Ascension Island in 1979. Typically, magnetic anomaly data are collected along east-west tracks at fixed track separations. Tracks of data are analyzed by searching for similar magnetic structures in adjacent tracks and determining the plate spreading rates and fault slippages which could cause these structures to take on their present forms. In the past this has been done by plotting sections of the tracks at various scales, physically overlaying the plots on a light table, and sliding the data around until similar structures match. Horizontal scale changes correspond to changes in spreading rates, and horizontal movement of one track relative to another corresponds to slippage along faults. Differences in vertical scale from track to track may be caused by local topographic features or by changes in the mineral content of the underlying structures. While the geophysical reasoning behind analysis of bathymetric and gravimetric data is different, the same type of data manipulation is often required.

The operations of repeatedly sliding data curves, overlaying them, rescaling data, etc., are tasks which suggest the use of interactive computer graphics techniques. The following sections will discuss an interactive graphics program written to allow the user to easily and rapidly perform this type of geometrical analysis of data profiles.

2. INTERACTIVE GRAPHICS

Interactive computer graphics has been called the most important mechanized means of producing and reproducing pictures since the invention of photography and television [3]. From aircraft flight simulation to molecular analysis, from newspaper layout to factory automation, interactive graphics is revolutionizing how man interprets and controls his environment.

Up until the late 1970's, each manufacturer provided a graphics software library to accompany his hardware. This library contained subroutines which defined the plotting operations allowed to the applications programmer. These libraries were generally limited in performance, did not contain the types of calls needed to perform interactive graphics conveniently, and could be applied only on the hardware of that manufacturer. Although this situation still exists to some

degree, the emergence of proposed software standards have begun to move graphics toward the goals of powerful software tools, device independence, and software portability.

There are two proposed graphics standards, the ACM Siggraph Core System (Core) and the Graphics Kernel System (GKS). Core was the initial attempt at defining a graphics standard [4]. GKS was developed in Europe utilizing some of the experience gained during the development of the Core system. However, due to the lack of then expensive color raster scan hardware in Europe, the powerful three-dimensional graphics capability of Core was not included in GKS. There is much diversity in the graphics community about the relative merits of these two standards [5,6]. As was noted, Core is fully three-dimensional, while GKS is two-dimensional (although a current, last minute effort is underway to overlay a three-dimensional capability on GKS). On the other hand GKS, building on Core, has greater formality including, for example, fully defined structure for subroutine calls (language bindings). There are also several useful additional two-dimensional capabilities in GKS. However, for the purpose of developing two-dimensional, interactive software to perform profile data analysis, either standard provides the required tools.

There will be many benefits for graphics users when a graphics standard is finally chosen. One major benefit will be that graphics programs will become portable from one machine to another in the same manner that, say, a FORTRAN program is currently portable. Even now, a program written using an implementation of either proposed standard has some limited portability. Since the interactive profile analysis program was written on a Hewlett-Packard 1000 series mini-computer using a Hewlett-Packard implementation of Core, the remainder of this paper will refer to Core, although, again, GKS also contains the required two-dimensional capability.

3. INTERACTIVE FEATURES OF CORE

Several features of Core allow the creation of powerful interactive graphics software. The first feature is the ability to create segments, i.e., labeled groups containing graphics primitives such as line drawing, text, and attribute setting. Once a segment has been created and closed, it may be addressed as an entity. In particular, operations such as replication of an individual segment on different portions of the plot, selection of objects using the graphics cursor, and selective erase become possible. Also, characteristics can be associated with segments. For example, a segment can be declared visible or invisible, detectable or not detectable.

Another very useful Core feature in designing interactive graphics programs is the automatic mapping from world (i.e., user defined) coordinates to normalized device coordinates (NDC).

Since output is always in NDC, it is easy to allow the user to redefine world coordinates, i.e., to rescale his data plots. The mapping to NDC makes windowing different display areas quite simple. Also, the internal computation is done in normalized coordinate space, which is unitless. Device independence can therefore be achieved by inserting, between Core and the output plotting device driver, a device handler which will convert from the NDC coordinates to appropriate scaling and characteristics for that output device.

In addition the graphics cursor can be used as a pick device to select segments or as a locator device to select points whose NDC values can be converted by Core into world coordinates. Hence, it becomes a simple task to allow the analyst to choose, for example, endpoints of a data segment for expansion.

4. THE INTERACTIVE ANALYSIS PROGRAM

The program was designed to plot up to four data profiles, each containing up to 2048 points. At most 256 data points from each profile may be visible at one time. However, so that larger profile sections may be examined, a profile may be decimated by a user selected factor (i.e., every n -th data point is used).

Figure 1 shows a typical situation. The primary menu, in the upper left, is always visible. Below the primary menu is a space where secondary menus appear when required. These menus apply primarily to user selection of points or curves and are made visible only when a selection from them is required. Displayed at the upper right are the current values of the y window, i.e., the minimum and maximum for the current y scale. The area at the upper left top is used for error and help messages. Four data tracks are seen. The bottom and next-to-bottom rectangles contain the first section (256 points) of airborne magnetic anomaly data from two parallel flights in an area over the Atlantic Ocean. The third and fourth rectangles contain the same data tracks, respectively, decimated by a factor of eight. Hence, the top two rectangles are displaying, in this case, the entire data tracks for the scientist. The numbers in the lower left and right of each rectangle are the latitude for the left and right data point of the displayed data section. User input is echoed on four lines at the lower left corner of the terminal screen.

The primary menu (see figure 1) contains options to perform those tasks which were previously done manually - sliding curves, overlaying curves, modifying plotting scales, and examining different sections of data. The options AC and RC are used to add and remove, respectively, a curve from the display. CF and CB allow stepping forward and backward, in 256 point sections, through one or all curves, while SL and SR slide a curve left or right an amount selected by the user via the graphics cursor. The graphics

Figure 1 - Atlantic Ocean airborne magnetic anomaly data.

cursor is also used for all curve selection. The EC option allows the user to expand a curve by selecting, with the cursor, two new endpoints. The OL option permits the user to cursor-select two curves which are then overlaid. The YW option allows the user to input new minimum and maximum y values, and the curves are then rescaled and quickly redrawn. The HC option allows the user to produce a hardcopy of the current display on the HP-2631G printer. In addition the user has other available options including the capability to write a curve section into a file for further mathematical analysis. All options which modify the display are accomplished in a few seconds.

Core permits, as was noted above, use of a pick device (e.g., the graphics cursor) for segment identification. Thus, selection from the primary menu could have been via the pick device. However, because the keyed movement of the graphics cursor on the HP-2647 terminal is both an inefficient and user unfriendly hardware device vis-a-vis the mouse or joystick [7], alphanumeric keyboard entry was selected instead. The graphics cursor is, as we have noted, used for selection of data curves and endpoints.

Because the user must perform many operations, it is especially important that interactive programs are user friendly. Otherwise, user frustration will result in non-utilization of potentially useful software. Typical methods for user assistance in interactive graphics include the use of icons (descriptive symbols denoting processes or actions), easily accessible help files for assistance, and extensive error checking within the program, including descriptive error messages. Figure 2 illustrates three icons. The arrow icon is used to point to that menu, I/O request or error message which requires user response. Since the magnetics data are contained in rather large ASCII files, reading

data into the program is often time consuming. So that the user will be aware of progress in reading the data file, a book icon is displayed. The pages of this book fill up with script as the reading progresses. This icon also, therefore, provides a measure of the file size. Similarly, a pen and paper icon is used to denote that internal plotting is taking place, since the visibility attribute is used to make plots visible only when completed. A help file is provided. This file is always callable as a primary menu option. Error messages, usually with corrective actions, appear in the upper left of the screen.

Figure 2 - Icons used by profile analysis program.

5. SAMPLE INTERACTIVE ANALYSIS

Figure 1, as discussed above, contains airborne magnetics data, plotted on a scale of -1000 to +1000 gammas. On examination the user will usually wish to rescale the data. To rescale, the analyst types YW and, in response to prompts, enters the new y scale of -500 to 200 gammas. The data is promptly redrawn to the new scale (figure 3). Now the user wishes to examine the region near the large negative peaks in both data tracks to determine if they are caused by the same bathymetric features. The analyst steps through the data on the two bottom curves using the CF and CB options and then slides the data left and right using the SL and SR options until the regions of interest are matched up. In each case the data are rapidly redrawn. Figure 4 shows the data after centering about the region of interest. Figure 5 illustrates the overlay (OL) option. In response to prompts the analyst uses the graphics cursor to select two curves, which are then overlaid. If the data curves match up well, the analyst can use the FC option to write the two lower curves to a data file for, say, correlation analysis. The curves to be filed would be chosen by using the graphics cursor in response to a program prompt. In this case the data was seen to be the central anomaly

Figure 3 - Data rescaling for greater resolution.

Figure 4 - Data centered about region of geographical interest.

Figure 5 - Overlay of Mid-Atlantic Ridge data from both tracks.

of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge and a more detailed analysis could proceed.

Figure 6 shows the effect of the expand curve (EC) option applied to the two lower curves. Using the graphics cursor, the user first selects a curve for expansion and then selects left and right endpoints for expansion. The curve is then redrawn with the new left endpoint at the left edge and the new right endpoint at the right edge. Thus, microfeatures in the data can be examined and compared. Figure 7 shows the effect of the OL option on the expanded data. The graphics cursor is again used, in response to messages, to pick the two curves to be overlaid.

Figure 6 - Expansion of the large negative peaks.

Figure 7 - Overlay of the expanded regions.

6. CONCLUSION

Interactive computer graphics provides a powerful tool for data analysis. Using techniques such as segmentation, point and object selection by pick and locator devices, and window and viewport modification, interactive programs can be created to perform tasks more rapidly and

with greater detail than previously possible. The use of icons, help files and extensive error checking results in easy-to-use software for the data analyst.

The establishment of graphics software standards will result in both hardware graphics device independence and portability of graphics programs (and programmers) between different computer systems. As a corollary, software producers will have a far larger market for their graphics products and can accordingly spend more time and money on product development. Hence the near future should see the availability of inexpensive software of the type discussed in this paper. The scientist involved in data analysis will gain by seeking out interactive graphics software suitable to his particular application.

Although interactive graphics programs require more development time than non-interactive ones, the savings which result by eliminating the need to perform repetitively a sequence of time consuming tasks justifies the extra development effort. In the end, interactive graphics programs such as the one described save the end user significant amounts of time and effort.

REFERENCES

1. LaCoste, L. et. al., "Gravity Measurements in an Airplane Using State-of-the-Art Inertial Navigation," Society of Exploration Geophysics Meeting, 1977.
2. Clamons, J. D., J. M. Brozena and L. J. Rosenblum, "A Marine Gravity Measurement System for Fixed Wing Aircraft," Proceedings of the Working Symposium on Oceanographic Computer Data Systems - 1983, Oct. 1983, pp.15-21.
3. Foley, J. D. and A. Van Dam, "Fundamentals of Interactive Computer Graphics," Addison-Wesley, 1982.
4. "Status Report of the Graphics Standards Committee," Computer Graphics, 11, 1977.
5. Wright, Thomas, "GKS Versus Core," Computer Graphics World, 7 (2), Feb. 1984, pp.18-24.
6. Sonderegger, E. L., "The Case for Core System Standardization," Computer Graphics World, 7 (2), Feb. 1984, pp. 26-30.
7. Card, S., W. K. English and B. J. Burr, "Evaluation of Mouse, Rate-controlled Isometric Joystick, Step Keys, and Text Keys for Text Selection on a CRT," Ergonomics, 21 (8), August 1978, pp. 601-613.